

Flavonoids of *Zizyphus rugosa*

A. Singh^a, M. B. Pandey^a, Sarita Singh^b, A. K. Singh^{b*} and J. P. Singh^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, S.G.R. Post Graduate College, (Purvanchal University, Jaunpur), Dobhi-222 149, Uttar Pradesh, India

^bDepartment of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : singhak06@rediffmail.com, Fax : 91-542-2367568

Manuscript received 28 May 2008, accepted 17 September 2008

Abstract : Three flavonoids – kaempferol-4'-methylether, luteolin and luteolin-7-O-glucoside have been isolated from the barks of *Zizyphus rugosa* and their structures were established by spectral evidences. This is the first report of these flavonoids from *Z. rugosa*.

Keywords : *Zizyphus rugosa*, flavonoids.

Introduction

The plant *Zizyphus rugosa* (Family : Rhamnaceae) is an evergreen shrub distributed throughout greater parts of India. It is used in Indian system of medicine for the treatment of diarrhoea, menorrhagia and in infection of teech¹. A number of terpenes²⁻⁴, terpen glycosides^{5,6}, sitosterols⁷, flavonoids^{3,5,7} and cyclopeptide alkaloids^{8,9} have earlier been reported from this plant. We report here the isolation and characterisation of three flavonoids from *Z. rugosa*.

Experimental

Dried powdered barks of *Z. rugosa* (2.5 kg) were extracted with MeOH in a Soxhlet extractor which on removal of solvent gave a brown gummy mass (95 g). The MeOH extract was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column eluting with solvents of increasing polarity and the collected eluants were monitored by thin layer chromatography. The eluantes from CHCl₃, CHCl₃-MeOH (50 : 1), CHCl₃-MeOH (20 : 1) and CHCl₃-MeOH (10 : 1) on crystallisation from MeOH furnished respectively the flavonoids, kaempferol-4'-methylether¹⁰ (1) as yellow granules, m.p. 226–228 °C; luteolin¹¹ (2) as yellow granules, m.p. 320–322 °C and luteolin-7-O-glucoside¹¹ (3) as yellow granules, m.p. 184–186 °C.

Compound (1) : UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) : 250sh, 268, 300, 320, 365 (log ϵ 4.16, 4.22, 3.71, 3.95, 4.30) nm; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3300–3600br, 1665 cm⁻¹; 90 MHz ¹H NMR

(DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 3.85 (3H, s, -OMe), 6.34 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-6), 6.72 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-8), 6.93 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 8.10 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 9.51 (1H, s, -OH, exchangeable with D₂O), 10.15 (1H, s, -OH, exchangeable with D₂O), 12.47 (1H, s, -OH, exchangeable with D₂O); HRMS, *m/z* (relative intensity %), 300.0632 ([M]⁺, calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂O₆, 100), 299 (49), 272 (25), 271 (33), 258 (35), 257 (48), 229 (20), 213 (10), 181 (24), 152 (10), 148 (20), 124 (5), 121 (15), 119 (25), 69 (28). Compound 1 on methylation with CH₂N₂ gave trimethyl derivative, m.p. 148–150 °C; C₁₉H₁₈O₆ (*m/z* 342.1100 [M]⁺) which showed three more methoxyl groups in ¹H NMR at δ 3.88, 4.15 and 4.24.

Compound (2) : UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) : 250, 267, 290sh, 350 (log ϵ 4.25, 4.22, 4.00, 4.33) nm; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3245–3450br, 1640, 1595 cm⁻¹; 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 6.26, 6.64 (1H, d, each, *J* 2 Hz, H-6, H-8), 6.82 (1H, s, H-3), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H-5'), 7.50 (1 H, dd, *J* 2.0 Hz, H-6'), 7.52 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-2'), 12.95 (1H, br s, -OH, exchanged with D₂O); MS, *m/z* (relative intensity %) : 286.0478 ([M]⁺, calcd. for C₁₅H₁₀O₆, 100), 258 (18), 257 (6), 229 (5), 153 (30), 152 (10), 134 (10), 129 (9), 124 (9), 69 (7). With Ac₂O and triethylamine the compound 2 furnished an acetate, m.p. 225–228 °C; C₂₃H₁₈O₁₀ (HRMS: *m/z* 454.0900 [M]⁺) which exhibited four acetate groups in ¹H NMR at δ 2.32 (3H, s, 1 × OAc), 2.33 (6H, s, 2 × OAc), 2.43 (3H, s, 1 × OAc).

Compound (3) : UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) : 254, 265, 294sh,

345 (log ϵ 3.56, 3.52, 3.26, 3.50) nm; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3200–3390br, 1642, 1594 cm^{-1} ; 90 MHz ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 3.30–4.00 (6H, m, glucosyl protons), 5.00 (1H, br s, anomeric-H), 6.45, 6.82 (1H, d, each, J 2 Hz, H-6, H-8), 6.76 (1H, s, H-3), 6.94 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5'), 7.50 (1H, dd, J 2, 9 Hz, H-6'), 7.53 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-2'), 12.95 (1H, br s, -OH); MS (relative intensity, %) m/z : 448.1000 (calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_{11}$, 1.5), 286 (100, base peak), 258 (15), 229 (8), 152 (7), 134 (12), 124 (8), 69 (5). Compound **3** was hydrolysed with aqueous HCl (6%) in MeOH for 4 h, which on working up furnished yellow granules, m.p. 322–325 °C, identified as luteolin (**2**) by IR, UV, ^1H NMR, MS and direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR). The sugar in the hydrolysate was identified as glucose by co-PC with authentic sample.

The structures of all the above compounds were supported by a study of the UV with shift reagents and direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. V. B. Pandey, Department

of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi for authentic samples.

References

1. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", eds. E. Blatter, J. F. Caisus and K. S. Mhaskar, 1975, **1**, p. 83.
2. R. L. Khosa, P. Meena and V. B. Pandey, *Indian Drugs*, 1987, **24**, 323.
3. Y. C. Tripathi, S. Devi, V. B. Pandey and A. H. Shah, *Fitoterapia*, 1988, **60**, 158.
4. N. Nahar, R. N. Das, M. Soeb, M. S. Marma, M. A. Aziz and M. Mosihuzzaman, *J. Bangladesh Acad. Sci.*, 1997, **21**, 151.
5. M. Kulshrestha and R. P. Rastogi, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 152.
6. V. B. Pandey and Y. C. Tripathi, *Fitoterapia*, 1993, **64**, 341.
7. V. B. Pandey, J. P. Singh, R. L. Khosa and A. H. Shah, *J. Chem. Soc. Pak.*, 1985, **7**, 33.
8. V. B. Pandey, Y. C. Tripathi, S. Devi, J. P. Singh and A. H. Shah, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, **27**, 1915.
9. Y. C. Tripathi, S. K. Maurya, V. P. Singh and V. B. Pandey, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 1563.
10. A. K. Singh, M. B. Pandey, V. P. Singh and V. B. Pandey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 297.
11. K. N. Singh, V. B. Pandey and A. H. Shah, *Fitoterapia* 1988, **60**, 78.